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Exploring the future of digital testing: How can multiple-choice and closed questions play a role in engineering education?

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Digitisation of learning also involves the digitisation of testing. With this comes certain challenges in terms of facilities, logistics, but most importantly, setting good testing items that align with curriculum goals. This is especially challenging in Mathematics (Sangwin and Köcher, 2016) and other application-based education that is foundational in Engineering Education.

At the end of the workshop, participants will be able to outline and contrast the different possibilities within digital testing. This will be achieved through the workshop sketching the background to why a technical university has decided to undertake digital testing in its current flexible Chromebook format ("Digital testing with chromebooks", n.d.), an interactive quiz regarding common misconceptions and truths about digital testing and two case studies of courses that use digital testing at the university. This includes a case study which combines classroom software and digital testing questions in order to facilitate authentic testing ("Digital assessment in Remindo", n.d.).

This information will be the foundation of the second half of the workshop, where participants will analyse and criticise undergraduate Mathematics multiple choice questions in terms of their learning goals, difficulty, and the effectiveness of the distractors (Anonymous, 2019). Participants will then be given guidelines to create and evaluate their own multiple-choice items for their own subject area. Participants will be able to have informed discussions and ideas regarding digital testing for their own specific education and have started creating items for their own subject areas.

Outline of Workshop (Max 50 participants):

1. General Introduction to Digital Testing (20 min)

- a. *Know:* What is meant by Digital Testing: Possibilities and question types.
- b. *Analyse:* Top 10 misconceptions and concerns quiz about digital testing.
- c. *Discuss:* Between presenters and participants
 - i. Why digital testing is done.
 - ii. Address concerns of digital testing.
 - iii. Present advantages of digital testing.

- d. *Understand*: Digital Testing at the university
 - i. When it started.
 - ii. Why Flexible model.
 - iii. Using Remindo for general testing and MyLabsPlus for Math.

2. Two examples (case studies) for digital testing (15min)

- a. *Understand*: Authentic testing using SPSS and Multiple Choice (Remindo)
 - i. How the cloud-computer solution can run both pieces of software in a secure environment, allowing for “open book” exams that uses Remindo in for the automatic assessment.
- b. *Understand*: MyLabsPlus
 - i. What content it has.
 - ii. Homework sessions and feedback to students, as well as video support.
 - iii. Allows for digital testing as it has mathematical equivalence reasoning.

3. Evaluation of MCQ in Mathematics – What makes a good distractor (20 min)

- a. *Know*: MCQ jargon.
- b. *Analyse*: Test validity and reliability: What are you testing, with focus on distractors.
- c. *Evaluation*: questions using rubric on thinking skills and difficulty.

4. Make your own item (25min)

- a. Participants make teams.
- b. *Create*: Participants are given a checklist to assist in creating items of their own.

5. Summarize and wrap-up (10 min)

- a. *Present*: Ideas of the future of digital testing.
- b. *Discuss*: Participants view of future of digital testing.